

The Analysis of Nanoptenna for Extreme Fast Communication (XFC) over Short Distance

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Abstract : This paper focuses on the analysis of Nanoptenna for extreme fast communication. The Nanoptenna is basically a nano antenna designed for communication at optical range of frequencies. Since, this range of frequencies includes the visible spectrum of the light, so there is a high possibility of the data transfer at high rates and extreme fast communication (XFC). The shape chosen for the analysis is a bow tie structure due to its various characteristics of electric field enhancement.

Keywords : nanoptenna, communication, optical range,XFC

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